

A STUDY ON DIGITAL MARKETING AND ITS IMPACT ON CONSUMERS PURCHASE**R. A. Jagtap***Assistant Professor in Commerce,**D.V.S College of Commerce, Koparkhairane, Navi Mumbai, University of Mumbai***ABSTRACT:**

Digital marketing is as a current type of marketing. Marketing activities undertaken through digital platforms allow marketers to connect directly with possible customers at a quick rate, irrespective of their topographical position. Online marketing has recently been described as one of the easiest ways to deal and interact directly with the buyer. Digital marketing is wide-based and includes developing business strategies to grow industry nationally and internationally in a highly competitive environment. Digital marketing has an imperative part to mounting the distribution of goods and services.

The purpose of this to examine the impact of digital marketing and whether it is an important tool for both companies & consumers. We have explored the effect of Digital Marketing as well as its impact on the customer's buying behavior. This study was performed on the basis of a structured questionnaire for primary data as well as a sample size of 150 respondents.

KEYWORDS-*Digital Marketing, Marketers, Distribution, Buying Behavior*

1. INTRODUCTION

Digital marketing is defined as the buying and selling of goods and services online. Digital marketing uses electronic platforms to meet the target audience. That Platforms are social net workings, blogs, online search engine, commercials, e-digital marketing, and multimedia advertisement. Digital Marketing often referred as online or web marketing. USA, Italy and UK are the countries using online marketing most commonly. In India after 1991 were starting to use online shopping reluctantly but during pandemic it is increase to 86% of the population in India

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Most significant measures of this transition from “Technology Development “that to new modern communication technologies are being used for "internet marketing.".

2. OBJECTIVES

1. To study the usefulness of Digital Marketing
2. To study the influence of digital marketing on consumers purchase

3. HYPOTHESIS OF THE RESEARCH STUDY

- 1) Digital Marketing reduces the gap between the Buyer and Sellers
- 2) The Digital Marketing helps to increase trading of goods and services positively.

4. METHODOLOGY APPLIED

- **Primary Data:** The study is done through observation collection of data through questionnaires.
- **Secondary Data:** Secondary data is collected from the various National and International Journals, Research Books and Magazines.
- **Sample Size:** The sample size is determined as 150 respondent's opinion from the customers who presently purchasing products with a help of digital marketing.

5. DIFFERENCES BETWEEN TRADITIONAL MARKETING AND DIGITAL MARKETING

Traditional Marketing:

- Traditional Marketing uses face-to-face, telephone lines, or mail systems.
- Traditional Marketing has to go all stages of business transactions
- It involves manual processing of traditional business transactions
- It is conventional type of marketing, best for reaching local audience.
- Campaigning takings more time for scheming, preparing, and launching.
- It is difficult to calculate the effectiveness of a campaign.

Digital -Marketing:

- It uses Internet or other network communication technologies.
- It brings together all activities of business transactions, like Marketing, Advertising as well as Service and Customer support
- Digital -marketing uses automated processing of business transactions.
- It is best for reaching global audience
- With digital tools, campaigning is easier. It is made to reach the particular audience by using search engine techniques.
- It is easier to measure the effectiveness of a campaign through analytics

5. ADVANTAGES OF DIGITAL MARKETING TO CONSUMERS AND ANALYSIS

a) Save time for customers

It helps to speeds up the buying process because it will be easy to buy specific product from online store which is very far and not easily available. Here how the Digital Marketing helps the customer to make available E- product easily and speedily.

b) Rapid and inexpensive marketing

Customers will not have to spend Much more money in market to buy the product online. There are many varieties shown about the single product.

c) Flexibility to buy product 24/7.

Digital Marketing provide platform to consumers for 24/7 local as well globally, services are available 24/7 and though helps to serve the services at anytime and anyplace. Providing helpdesk to the customers for the any queries, recommendation about the products

d) Product and Price comparison possible

Customers can compare the products easily by studying different web sites and shares a detail description with other customers. The most useful part of Digital Marketing is that Consumers can avail and understand the product clearly that not happens at physical store.

e) Geographical restriction.

Customer can access online store from wherever in the world, which can worldwide be accessed. If customers are not able to find a particular product which not available at the store location but through online store provide them with multiple options. So, that they can avail the services easily.

f) Reviews Available Geographical restriction

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h) Reviews Available

Recommendations and review which can give different standard to buy and to sell the product and help customers to build more trust over a particular product. It can help the buyers to be clear and more visible about the product that helps buyers with more product selection.

5. CONSUMERS ANALYSIS

Table 1: Profile of the Online Buyers

Elements	Category	Number of Respondents	Percentage of Respondent
Gender	Male	80	53.3%
	Female	70	46.7%
	Total	60	100
Age	Below 21 Years	67	44.7%
	21-30 years	34	35.3%
	31-45 year	38	25.3%
	Above 45 years	11	7.3%
	Total	150	100
Profession	House Wife	NA	NA
	Employee	21	81.3%
	Business	2	1.4%
	Students	122	14%
	Any other	5	3.3%
	Total	150	100
Monthly Family Income (in Rs.)	Below 15000	38	25.3%
	15001-25000	100	66.7%
	25001-40000	7	4.7%

	Above 40000	5	3.3%
	Total	150	100

Table 2: Awareness of Online Shopping

Particulars	Number of Respondents	Percentage of Respondents
Having knowledge about online shopping	137	91.3%
Not having knowledge about online shopping	13	8.7
Total	150	100

Table 3: Online Information about Product

Particulars	Number of Respondents	Percentage of Respondents
Excellent	24	16%
Good	93	62%
Average	28	18.7%
Poor	5	3.3%
Total	150	100

Table 4: Reasons for Selecting Online Shopping

Particulars	Number of Respondents	Percentage of Respondents
Wide variety of Products	37	24.7%
Easy buying Procedures	47	31.3%
Lower Prices	28	18.7%
Various Modes of Payments	29	19.3%
Others	09	6%
Total	150	100

Table 5: Frequency of Online Buying

Particulars	Number of Respondents	Percentage of Respondents
Purchase once Annually	54	36%
2 - 4 Purchases Annually	52	34.7%
5-10 Purchases Annually	32	21.3%
11 Purchases and above Annually	12	8%
Total	150	100

Table 6: Reports on Customers Satisfaction on Online Buying

Particulars	Number of Respondents	Percentage of Respondents
Strongly Agree	47	31.33%
Agree	93	62%
Disagree	2	1.33%
Neutral	7	4.67
Strongly Disagree	1	0.67
Total	150	100

Table 7: Reports on Customers Satisfaction on Online Buying

Particulars	Number of Respondents	Percentage of Respondents
Convenience Goods	29	19.33%
Shopping Goods	97	64.67%
Specialty Goods	24	16%
Total	150	100

6. FINDINGS

- Digital marketing has a better future in the existing market.
- Consumers are satisfied through buying digital marketing.
- People feel safe to buy online
- There is no big difference between Male and Female customers in online shopping.
Male: 53.3% and Female: 46.7%
- Awareness about online shopping is 91.3% among the respondents. 8.7% have not online awareness, are those especially house wife and above age of 45 years.
- Income of respondents mainly falls in the range of 15001-25000/- are 66.7%
- Employees of various companies (including Male and Female) are purchasing more than others through online shopping that is 81.4%.
- Most numbers of respondents that is 31.3% feels that online shopping have simple buying procedures; 24.7% respondents feel that they can have a broad variety of products, 19.3% respondent are interested in variety mode of payments. 18.7% respondents feels that products with lower price,
- 62% of respondents feel that availability of online information about Product & Services is outstanding.

- 34.7% of the respondents purchase the products 2 to 4 time. 36% of the respondents purchase the products for single time as they have interest or wonder purpose buying products online.
- 62% of the respondents are seem to be satisfied with purchase the products through online and respondents unsatisfied reports are very less or negligible.
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- More than 60% respondents are interested to buy shopping goods through online while response for Convenience Goods and Specialty Goods are comparatively low .

5. SUGGESTIONS

- 1) Have to create awareness among the people about digital marketing.
- 2) Efforts to be taken to encourage Female buyer specially House wife.
- 2) Need of technical improvement in promotion of digital marketing.
- 3) Provide a transparent service to the consumer before and after buying.
- 4) Collect and implement the feedback provided by the consumer in the right way.
- 5) Encourage people to buy Convenience goods and Specialty goods as well.

6. CONCLUSION

Digital marketing has play very important part to approach customers for many companies. At the present time, Digital Marketing helps to reduce the gap between buyer (consumers) and the sellers (companies) so the consumers can get products and services directly to their hand only. Business proprietor from remote area can sells the products by using an inexpensive and competent method of digital marketing, similarly consumers also have an opportunity to have that produce very easily. In other words, we can say that Digital Marketing helps to increase goods and services positively. It has no restrictions. Business can use any devices such as smart phones, TV, laptops, media, social media, email and lot other to support company and its products and services.

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